

Reuse and Recycle of Outgoing Electronic Gadgets - A Comprehensive Review and Proposal for a Novel Solution

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Abstract: Various terminologies like "e-waste," "electronic garbage," "e-scrap," and "end-of-life electronics" are frequently used to refer to the electronics already been used that are close to reaching the end of their useful lives and are discarded, donated, or sent to a recycler. As compared to the traditional municipal wastes, certain components of electronic products contain various toxic substances, which can generate a serious threat to the environment as well as to human health. Now for example, television and computer monitors usually contains health hazardous materials such as lead, mercury, and cadmium, while nickel, beryllium, and zinc can often be found in circuit boards. As these substances are present, recycling and disposal of e-Waste becomes an important issue. People are gravely concerned about how used electronics and e-waste are handled inadvertently in underdeveloped nations, endangering both human health and the environment. Electronic gadgets are meant to make our lives happier and simpler, but due to the toxicity they contain, their disposal and recycling becomes a crucial health nightmare. Most of the users are unaware of the negative consequence of rapidly increasing use of computers, monitors, and televisions. Therefore, business officials as well as waste management officials are facing new challenges in an alarming rate, and e-Waste or waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) is receiving considerable attention from policy makers. The phrase used to describe e-waste is "recycle it everything, no matter how little". By stopping people from discarding their threshold electronic products and by making internet gadgets accessible to the poor populations, we hope to alleviate two problems at once. In this process, we hope to focus on making the environment eco-friendly.

Keywords: E Waste, Recycle, Reuse, WEEE, Electronic Gadgets, Upcycling, Waste Reduction, Sustainability, Resource conservation, Responsible Consumption.

Introduction

Present-day watches, cigarettes, scooters, and even books have all evolved into electronic devices. With so many alternatives available, there is a push to always upgrade to the most recent version. In such a case, how can you recycle those outdated electronics? That old phone, laptop, or tablet aren't even something you need anymore. It's time to get rid of it!

As there does not seem to be a standard definition for E-waste, Sinha-Khetriwal has defined in a way saying that, "E-waste can be classified as any electrically powered appliance that has reached its end-of-life". There are approximately 6.9 billion mobile users, almost as many as people on earth. People who are excessively using electronic gadgets develop musculoskeletal disorders (Needhidasan et al, 2014). Repetitive strain injury is a chronic condition that has been developed because of the repetitive, forceful, or awkward hand movements for prolonged duration that will lead to damage of muscles, tendons, and nerves of the neck, shoulder, forearm, and hand, which can cause pain, weakness, numbness, or impairment of motor control. E-waste is made up of a variety of components with valuable resources, some of which contain poisonous compounds that might be harmful to both human health

and the environment. According to earlier research, India produced 0.4 million tonnes of e-waste in 2010, and that number might rise to 0.5 to 0.6 million tonnes by 2013–2014 (Sarla et al, 2019). E-waste management in India has been significantly impacted by the absence of proper infrastructure facilities and processes for its disposal and recycling.

It started off making radios, but it has since expanded into new fields like computer systems, defence technology, communication, medical diagnosis, and space exploration. It is a tertiary occupation that is rapidly expanding and is more prevalent in southern areas.

Over the past 20 years, the electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) industry has experienced rapid growth. India's electronics sector has the potential to become one of the top exporters in the next three to five years. This paves as a new dilemma for both industry and waste management officials; and policymakers are paying close attention to e-Waste, i.e., waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE).

If an old gadget isn't working correctly, think about having it fixed rather than tossing it away. Repairing damaged devices may offer them a new lease on life. There are several ways to fix, use again, and recycle as a consequence. Spot a nearby repair facility. Even if our phones and tablet phones cannot be rebuilt, there are many other devices that can be repaired and used. This is called best out of waste. Barter services with a handyman guy. Locate a friend, neighbor, or co-worker who is skilled in electronics repair. Do the repairs yourself.

Deliver your usable electronics to a donation location. Any useable products that can be sold again are accepted by organizations like Goodwill and Salvation Army. Just drop them off is all that is required. If you have a sizable donation, they might occasionally come to your house and take it up. Consult with organizations in your neighborhood. Internet-based device sales. Additionally, several types of businesses will pay you cash for used electronics that you mail them, and they will refurbish and sell.

The best way to help people behave more responsibly towards the environment is to educate them about how to recycle, reuse, and dispose of electronics at all levels. Electronic trash is, in fact, a global issue that needs a worldwide solution. So, in this article, we'll talk more about managing electronic wastes and strategies and various alternatives that have been implemented to cut down on the generation of E-waste.

Fig.1: Main contributors to E-Waste , (www.statista.com)

History

Electronic waste, commonly referred to as e-waste, has been a persistent environmental concern for several decades. With the exponential growth of technology and the digital age, the volume of electronic waste being generated globally has increased significantly, and so has the need for its proper disposal. The improper disposal of e-waste poses a considerable risk to human health and the environment due to the presence of hazardous substances like lead, mercury, and cadmium.

The Resource Conservation and Recovery Act (RCRA) of 1976 was a crucial turning point in the proper disposal and recycling of electronic waste. The Act aimed to protect the environment and human health from the risks associated with garbage disposal and to preserve natural resources, including energy (Kovacs et.al 1976) (Andersen et. al. 1978). It also sought to contribute to reducing waste production and ensure that all garbage is handled in an environmentally friendly manner. To achieve these objectives, the EPA established three distinct but linked programs-the underground storage tank program, the hazardous waste program, and the program for solid waste.

In the 1980s, incidents of illegal dumping of electronic waste in developing countries by developed nations came to light, bringing international attention to the issue (Hall et. al. 2001). One such instance occurred when a Liberian ship was hired to transport and dispose of 14,000 tonnes of electronic waste ash from Philadelphia. When New Jersey refused to receive the ash, the ship dumped the waste haphazardly into the water all the way from the Caribbean to Asia (Siddique et. al. 2019). Another incident happened in Nigeria, where electronic waste was dumped in landfills, causing significant environmental and health hazards. These illicit dumping practices prompted the international community to establish dumping laws to ensure proper disposal of e-waste (Islam et. al. 2020). The

Basel Convention, an international agreement to regulate the movement of hazardous waste between countries, was established in 1989. The convention aimed to reduce the movement of hazardous waste from developed to developing countries and to ensure proper management and disposal of e-waste. The convention has been ratified by 186 countries, including the European Union, and signed by the US and Haiti, but not yet ratified (Rosenthal et al., 1992).

The evolution of e-waste management has been significant since the enactment of the RCRA and the establishment of the Basel Convention. Recycling has grown from a small-scale endeavor to a significant global industry with a vested interest in preserving the environment. Various stakeholders, including governments, organizations, and individuals, have stepped up their efforts to ensure the proper management and disposal of e-waste. (Baldé et al, 2017). Several recycling initiatives and programs have been launched globally, emphasizing the need to reduce, reuse and recycle electronic waste. Companies and organizations have implemented e-waste recycling policies, which require the proper disposal of electronic equipment at the end of its useful life. Many manufacturers are adopting eco-design principles, which incorporate the entire life cycle of a product, from design to end-of-life disposal (Sarkis et al, 2010). Despite these efforts, e-waste continues to be a significant environmental problem, with a large volume of electronic waste still being improperly disposed of globally. The proliferation of electronic devices and the rise of e-commerce have only added to the volume of e-waste generated. As such, there is a need for more comprehensive e-waste management policies, including extended producer responsibility, eco-design, and take-back programs, to address this issue (Kahhat et al, 2012).

In conclusion, the proper disposal and management of e-waste are essential to protect human health and the environment. The enactment of the RCRA and the establishment of the Basel Convention were significant milestones in the proper disposal of electronic waste. Recycling has grown from a small-scale endeavor to a significant global industry with a vested interest in preserving the environment. However, more comprehensive policies and initiatives are needed to address the challenges associated with e-waste and ensure the sustainable management of electronic equipment at the end of its useful life.

Current Solutions to the Problem

Waste Electrical and Electronics Equipment is the fastest growing waste stream in the world (Herat et al., 2007). Once an electrical component is regarded as obsolete, it is generally either leached to retrieve the precious metals from it and then discarded into landfills or incinerated. Reuse is a broad term used to refer to lengthening the life span of a piece of equipment before it ultimately has to be discarded (Renteria et al., 2009). Another approach is recycling, which involves using functional parts of a piece of equipment for other purposes similar to, or different to than the purpose it was originally intended for. Considering its rising relevance, several measures have been implemented across the world (table 1)

Table 1: A few implemented current solutions to the problem

1. Project AutDem: Developed by the University of Berlin, this project focuses on the disassembly of Surface Mounted Devices (SMDs), from which useful and toxic components are separated. Metallic and Non - metallic components are separated by magnetic fields or gravity separation techniques. Nonmetals may be used in construction work, composite boards, sewer grates, etc (Stobbe. Et. al, 2004).
2. Several countries have introduced legislative initiatives such as having fee systems in place for the takeback of large appliances. This includes countries like Japan, Taiwan and Canada (where provinces with authority to require takeback of electronics cover about 95% of the population.) (Realff et. al., 2004). Environment Canada regulates the policies regarding toxic waste disposal, handling and is also responsible for development of technical documents about municipal waste generation and disposal (Kumar et. Al., 2016).
3. Nontox: This scheme aims to describe the proper technologies to be used in responsible management of electronic wastes i.e., those in compliance with the European WEEE Directive, as well as to describe the improper practices taking place (Ardolina et al.).
4. Startups like Rubicon Global, Aihuishou, Back market exist with the aim of refurbishing and selling electronic goods, or with selling secondhand equipment (Wilts et al., 2019) (Wang et al., 2018).
5. Electronics Waste Recycling Act: Implemented in California, 2003, to minimize the use of hazardous metals in electronic products. Electronic recycling is also imposed on new purchases of electronics products. These returns go towards future recycling of these electronics (Bergner et al., 2004).
6. ERC system (E-Waste Recycling Credits): An initiative of the Indian Government which gives formal organizations incentives for reducing and reusing their E waste. These E- credits can then be used to offset energy utility bills (Yu et al., 2010).

Table 1: A few implemented current solutions to the problem

The Rise of Online Society

The rise of online society has been a significant shift in the way people interact and engage with each other. With the increasing accessibility of the internet, social media, and digital media, more people are using online platforms to connect, express themselves, and consume information (Livingstone et al., 2010). This shift has created new forms of social interaction and community, transforming the way people connect and engage with each other. One of the primary drivers of the rise of online society is the increasing availability and accessibility of the internet. As internet connectivity has become more widespread, more people have access to online platforms and communities. This has led to the emergence of new forms of social interaction, such as online dating, social networking, and online gaming (M. Kaplan et al., 2010). Social networking sites like Facebook and Twitter have also become popular platforms for people to connect with friends and family, share information, and engage in social and political discourse. Another factor contributing to the rise of online society is the growing importance of digital media in people's lives (Smith et al., 2021). As more people consume news, entertainment, and other forms of media online, the internet has become a primary source of information and socialization for many. Online media has also created new opportunities for creativity and expression, allowing individuals to share their ideas and opinions with a broader audience (Abdulla et al., 2018).

However, the rise of online society has also had negative impacts on individuals and society. The spread of misinformation, hate speech, and other forms of online abuse has become a significant issue in the online world. The ease with which information can be shared and disseminated online has led to the proliferation of fake news and conspiracy theories, which can have serious consequences for individuals and society (Fard et al., 2022) (Gorell et al., 2018). The anonymity and distance of online interactions can also make it easier for individuals to engage in abusive or harmful behavior. Despite these challenges, the rise of online society has also brought many positive changes. It has enabled people to connect with others who share their interests and values, creating new opportunities for social and political engagement. Online communities have become platforms for activism and social change, allowing individuals to mobilize and raise awareness about important issues. Online education has also become a popular way for people to gain new skills and knowledge, regardless of their location or socioeconomic status (DiGrazia et al., 2013). As the internet continues to evolve and new technologies emerge, the nature of online society is likely to continue changing as well. The rise of virtual reality and augmented reality, for example, may create new forms of social interaction and community. The increased use of artificial intelligence in online platforms may also transform the way people engage with online media and each other. It is important for individuals and society as a whole to stay aware of these changes and adapt to them in a responsible and ethical manner (Kim et al., 2019).

In conclusion, the rise of online society has been a significant shift in the way people interact and engage with each other. While it has brought many positive changes, it has also created new challenges, such as the spread of misinformation and online abuse. As the internet and digital media continue to evolve, it is essential for individuals and society as a whole to stay aware of these changes and adapt to them in a responsible and ethical manner. By doing so, we can ensure that the rise of online society continues to bring positive changes and benefits for all.

Future Challenges

The economic benefits of using a circular economic model for e-waste are emerging. According to recent estimates, about 50 million tons of e-waste is thrown away each year (Islam et al., 2016). Just around 20% of this garbage is recycled (Rao et al., 2007). Every year, the volume of abandoned electronics increases by 2.5 million tons. The e-waste sector is predicted to increase to approximately 75 million tonnes by 2030 (Forti et al., 2020), more than tripling the present yearly garbage production. This increase is most likely due to more people purchasing items with shorter life cycles and fewer repair alternatives for older technologies. MRFs face difficulties in recycling or otherwise breaking down electrical waste (Material Recycling Facilities). E-waste is difficult to process and filter for a variety of reasons (Bakshi et al., 2019).

Several forms of e-waste have complicated products, making efficient material separation and sorting challenging. Glass, different polymers, ferrous and non-ferrous metals, and other materials are used to make electronics. To treat the e-waste, the recycler must separate smaller and bigger components and prevent combining different materials. There are many steps in this process: Dismantling electronics to remove batteries and other hazardous waste (Zhang et al., 2018). Shredding or crushing the remaining electronic components into smaller sizes. Separating fine materials, like small plastic or glass pieces, from larger scrap metals. Sorting the metals into various types, e.g., separating ferrous from non-ferrous. Removing glass fines from plastics fines.

But now comes another inherent challenge in this process which is exclusively known as efficiency. E-waste output is increasing in tandem with the rising manufacturing of consumer gadgets. As a result, MRFs must adjust to growing production needs on a continuous basis. Excessive product complexity and inadequate screening result in a visible contamination problem. Greater material purity requirements are being created, putting a greater responsibility on MRFs to deliver a cleaner product (Wang et al., 2019). This implies less material mixing and stricter processing. Systems with large volume processing capabilities and an equally high level of e-waste screening efficiency are required. Several old technologies are unable to fulfil these demands. International conventions such as the Basel Convention strive to reduce and regulate the transfer of hazardous waste between states (Liu et al., 2016). Even with the Convention, illicit shipping and disposal of e-waste continues. It is projected that 50 million

tones of e-waste were created globally in 2016. Personal gadgets such as computers, displays, cell phones, tablets, and televisions account for half of this, with the remaining being bigger household appliances and heating and cooling equipment.

Proposed Business Model

The business model runs as follows: Take for example an upper middle-class man who has a smartphone. Although the average lifespan of a phone is 3 to 4 years, the man plans on discarding his existing phone in favour of a newer model. He has two options, either to completely discard the gadget, or to sell it as a second-hand device on eBay.

The company aims to give the user another option. By donating his phone to the company, he will receive a portion of its original cost. The device will then be cleaned out, emptied, and optimized. Depending on its physical and internal condition, the amount of compensation to the donator will vary. These devices will then be sold to people from underprivileged backgrounds at a much lower cost than market value.

Firstly, the fact that a large portion of the population does not have access to phones and electrical gadgets, despite them becoming an integral part of society. How much a community has progressed technologically can be closely related to how much of its population has access to the latest technologies (Schaffer et.al, 2006). Though once seen as luxuries, smartphones can quickly advance a community by providing them access to communication and the internet at the most basic level. Keep in mind that this kind of business model will only work in those societies that have already had their basic needs met (For example, food, water electricity).

The second issue solved by our company is that of electronic waste. In the above example, the man could choose to discard his device, contributing to an ongoing pileup of e-waste. Most of this does not go into reuse or recycling, but rather into landfills where they do not degrade. By reusing gadgets that are in relatively good condition, we prolong their lifespan which ultimately reduces the need to throw them into landfills.

Once the device is handed in at one of our outlets or by pickup, it is taken back to a facility where it is scanned and examined. The donor is compensated for his contribution. Then, the device is cleaned and restored to factory settings by team members/volunteers. It is then repackaged and sold to members of underprovided communities for a fraction of its original cost. The difference between the compensation cost and the sales price provides sustenance to the company (Griskevicius et.al.).

Fig. 2: Proposed Business Model

Financial and Future Planning

Recurring costs: Rent of headquarters, Travel fees, employment fees, licensing expenditures, packaging materials, storage facilities, etc.

Short term plan: To procure profit from each device we sell, and to reinvest this profit into the company, growing it and upgrading its facilities while also providing volunteer fee and managing other recurring expenses (McKeever, 2018). Compensating donors according to an appropriate grading scale of which an example is as follows.

Very good condition: 15% of original cost
 Good condition : 10% of original cost
 Decent condition : 8% original cost
 Poor condition : 5% of original cost
 Very poor condition : No compensation

Medium term plan: To grow the company, upgrade its facilities, and spread its reach to beyond the original location. Expand the range of gadgets that are available to donate and set up more centers and pickup locations (Ionut et.al., 2015).

Long term plan: To further expand the reach of the company to international levels, build on profits to enhance donation experiences, hire micro specialised employees to manage each step of the process. Serve more communities and aim to place a smartphone in the hands of all those who will be benefited by it. (Qastharin et.al., 2016).

6.3 Unique Selling Point of the Company

Our company recognizes the growing significance of electronic gadgets in our daily lives and the critical role they play in shaping our society. However, it is also imperative to acknowledge the impact of their disposal on the environment and the potential harm it can cause to backward communities. Our aim is to bridge this gap by encouraging individuals to donate their old electronic gadgets instead of discarding them and channeling these resources to uplift underprivileged communities. Our company believes in the power of technology to bring about positive change and strives to make a difference through our unique approach (Lee et al., 2022). One of the major challenges that we face is the lack of accessibility and awareness among people regarding donation facilities. We aim to create a more streamlined process by providing easy access to donation centres and raising awareness about the importance of reusing electronic gadgets. Our social enterprise is not only focused on doing good but also on creating a sustainable business model that benefits everyone involved. We offer a financial incentive for individuals who donate their gadgets, which serves as a win-win situation for both parties involved. The financial benefit may not be significant, but the knowledge that their contribution is making a difference is far more rewarding for most donors (Byrne et.al., 2005). In addition to contributing to a noble cause, our company is also committed to reducing electronic waste at the local level. We believe that small steps can lead to big changes, and by encouraging individuals to donate their old electronic gadgets, we can help reduce the amount of e-waste that ends up in landfills (Adisa et al , 2021). We believe that access to basic facilities and technology can open up a world of opportunities for individuals in underprivileged communities. By reusing electronic gadgets, we can help bridge the digital divide and provide a platform for communities to connect and thrive. With a little education and support, we can empower these communities to create a better future for themselves and their families. (Yu et al ,2013). In conclusion, our company sees the potential of electronic gadgets in creating a positive impact on society while also acknowledging the potential harm they can cause to the environment and underprivileged communities. Our social enterprise aims to fill this gap by creating a streamlined process for electronic gadget donation, reducing e-waste, and providing access to technology for underprivileged communities.

Conclusion

Recycling electronic waste is becoming increasingly important as the number of electronic devices continues to rise. As these devices become more advanced, they also become more difficult to recycle, creating an even greater need for responsible e-waste management. In addition to preventing environmental destruction, recycling electronic waste has many other benefits (M. Maksimovic et al ,2018). One benefit of recycling e-waste is that it conserves natural resources. Many electronic devices contain valuable metals such as copper, gold, and silver that can be extracted and reused. Recycling these materials reduces the need to extract new resources from the environment, which can be expensive and environmentally damaging. Recycling electronic waste also helps to reduce energy costs. Manufacturing new electronic devices requires a significant amount of energy, much of which comes from non-renewable sources. By recycling old devices, the energy required to extract and process raw materials for new devices is reduced, which in turn reduces energy costs and helps to promote more sustainable manufacturing practices. Another benefit of recycling electronic waste is that it helps to promote a circular economy. Rather than disposing of old devices, which often end up in landfills or incinerators, recycling allows these materials to be reused in new products which gives them a new lease of life. This helps to create a closed loop where waste is minimized and resources are conserved. Despite the numerous benefits of recycling e-waste, many people still do not do so. One reason for this is that e-waste recycling can be complicated and time-consuming. However, there are many resources available to help people recycle their electronic waste, including drop-off locations, mail-in programs, and community recycling events. Recycling electronic waste is an important step that individuals and businesses can take to protect the environment and promote sustainability. By conserving natural resources, reducing energy costs, and promoting a circular economy, recycling e-waste helps to ensure a brighter future for our planet and all of its inhabitants. As responsible global citizens, it is our duty to do our part in reducing our carbon footprint and making a positive impact on the world.

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